

UNDERSTANDING LIFESTYLE DISEASES: UNDER THE UMBRELLA OF AYURVEDA

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ABSTRACT

Lifestyle disorder - a new era disease category disease that resulted from derangement in our living pattern. Unhealthy eating habits, lack of physical activity (inactivity) and disrupted biological clocks, etc. few of many reasons behind the development of life style disorders. The common lifestyle disorders which are currently being diagnosed include hypertension, obesity, diabetes mellitus, cardiovascular disease and atherosclerosis, etc. In Ayurvedic perspective the main causes of lifestyle disorders is *Pragy-apradha* and *AsatmyaIndriyarthasamyog, Parinam*. Ayurveda offers comprehensive ways of managing lifestyle disorders through *Dinacharya, Ritucharya, and Pathya apathyavichar*. This article discusses general aspects of lifestyle disorders as per Ayurveda and modern perspectives.

KEYWORDS: *Lifestyle Disorders, Obesity, Diabetes Mellitus, Dosha, Cardiovascular Disease.*

INTRODUCTION

The term lifestyle disorder describes illnesses related directly to a health problems that develop when an individual moves away from healthy habits toward an unhealthy lifestyle routine.

Ayurveda, which is among the ancient sciences of life, has at its core a fundamental principle of health, it describeshita ayu and balance between the physical (*Sharirika*) and mental (*Mansika*) *Doshas*. In Ayurvedic philosophy, both the type of food (*Ahara*) and the way it is eaten are equally important. The form of the food substance and the type of taste (*Rasa*), nature of the qualities (*Guna*), strength of the potency (*Virya*), and post-digestive effect (*Vipaka*) determine the balance of the *Doshas* and *Dhatus* in the body. Whenever this balance get disrupted by imbalanced living pattern then many diseases such as *Madhumeha, Sthaulaya, Hridroga* and *Apasmara/Manasika Vyadhi*, etc. may arises.

Pathological Aspect

In the contemporary time, lifestyles disorders have been increased due to improper diets, sedentary living, smoking, lack of sleep, excess alcohol intake and stress. It leads to improper nourishment, medicines alone cannot sustain life. Since the *Vedic* era, *Ahara* has had an

important place in Ayurveda for health maintenance. In Ayurveda, *Ahara, Nidra* and *Brahmacharya* are together known as *TrayaUpastambha*, which are three supports of life and health. *Ahara* not only sustains life but also provides ayu *Bala, Varna,oja* Whenever this *Ahara* become inappropriate either in the *matra, kala* (time) or way of taking food then this causes adverse effect and becomes major cause of life style disorders. **Figure 1** depicted major pathological events related to the life style disorders according to Ayurveda.^[4-6]

Figure 1: Pathological aspect related to the lifestyle disorders.

Etiology of Lifestyle Disorders

Other than infectious cause, reason for disease are mainly aharaj and viharaj. Poor eating patterns like Adhyasan - eating after meal lead to ajeeran and aama. Aama is undigested food which remains in our body producing toxic material leads to diabetes mellitus, cardiovascular disease, and stroke. In the present time lack of outdoor activity leads to minimized exposure to natural sunlight and fresh air increases the chance of acquiring a lifestyle diseases. The major contributing causes of lifestyle disorders according to Ayurveda are depicted in Table 1.^[5-7]

Table 1: Major contributing causes of lifestyle disorders according to Ayurveda.

Category of <i>Nidana</i>	Specific Causes
<i>Aaharaja Nidana</i>	<i>Atiruksha</i>
	<i>Atisnigdha</i>
	<i>Guru Bhojana</i>
	<i>Ajeernashana</i>
<i>Viharaja Nidana</i>	<i>Vegavidharana</i>
	<i>Ratrijagarana</i>
	<i>Diwaswapana</i>
	<i>Langhana</i>
<i>Manasika Nidana</i>	<i>Dvesha</i>
	<i>Krodha</i>
	<i>Bhaya</i>
	<i>Shoka</i>

Thus, lifestyle disorders are multifactorial in origin, resulting from improper diet, faulty lifestyle practices, and psychological stressors. Maintaining a balanced diet, proper daily routine and mental well-being is essential for preventing the onset and progression of lifestyle-related diseases.

Role of Life Style Factors in Disease Development^[5-8]

- ✓ Unhealthy *Ahara* disturb balance of doshas, decrease *Agni* power, forms *Ama* and ultimately resulting in diseases. Dietary factors resulting from *Prajnaparada* are:
 - *ViruddhBhojan* - Incompatible food combinations
 - *Dusta Bhojan* - Polluted/Spoiled food.
 - *AsuchiBhojan* - Impure Food.

These effects lead to *Agnimandya* (sluggish digestion), formation of *Ama*, and metabolic disorders.

- ✓ Unwholesome *Vihara* habits include irregular daily routine, excessive physical/mental exertion, *Vegadharana*, lack of exercise, excessive sensory indulgence, *Ratrijagarana* or *Divasvapna*. These behaviours vitiate *Vata*, *Pitta*, and *Kapha* balance causing systemic disruption.
- ✓ Disturbing *Dinacharya* and *Ritucharya* interrupts the normal cycles within the body. Failure to live according to times, seasons and individual *Prakriti* patterns creates aggravated *Doshas* and weakens the immune system (*Ojas Kshaya*).

- ✓ Psychological Effects (*Manasika Vihara*) such as stress, anxiety, anger, greed, and fear, indulgence in virtual world of social media, mobile phone contributes towards the disorder development. Disturbance of *Rajas* and *Tamas* due to *Manasika Nidanas* contributes to psychosomatic disorders and sleep disorders. Mental disturbances primarily vitiate *Vata Dosha*, leading to psychosomatic disorders. Various *Manasika Nidana* are as follows:

Mental factor	<i>Dosha</i> involvement
<i>Shrama</i> (mental stress)	<i>Vata</i>
<i>Kama</i> (excess desire)	<i>Vata</i>
<i>Chinta</i> (worry)	<i>Vata</i>
<i>Bhaya</i> (fear)	<i>Vata</i>
<i>Krodha</i> (anger)	<i>Vata</i>
<i>Shoka</i> (grief)	<i>Vata-Pitta</i>

- ✓ **Sedentary Lifestyle** results in an accumulation of *Kapha*, creating a disruption in *Medadhātu* and leading to disorders like *Sthaulya*, *Prameha*, and dislipidemia.
- ✓ **Asatmya Indriya-Artha-Samyoga** would be the unhealthy bond between the Bodily Senses and the Sensory Objects of the Bodily Senses. It occurs in three types, *Ati* and *Hina* Yoga will refer to the Excessive and Deficient (“Under-Utilized”) bond with the Bodily Senses; and *Mithya* Yoga will refer to an improper bond that can lead to toxic weight, a poor quality of life, and to illness and disease.
- ✓ **Prajnaparadha**: The term *Prajnaparadha* refers to a situation where a person willfully allows themselves to hurt themselves or others through an action (e.g., drugs) that is damaging to themselves or others. Most of the time this happens due to not following *Aacharrasayan* as described in Ayurveda leads to person's intellectual capacity being reduced due to an impaired capacity for *Dhibramāsa* the ability to think clearly, make decisions and take appropriate actions and also *Dhriti bramāsa* which is the ability to control oneself when negatively stimulated.
- ✓ **Three basic desires (Eshana)** In terms of both spiritual and physical health, *Charaka* identifies three basic desires:
 1. The desire to live (*Praneshana*).
 2. The desire for wealth (*Dhaneshana*).
 3. The desire for a righteous afterlife (*Paralokeshana*).
- ✓ Pursuing these desires excessively or improperly will result in a person's *Prajnaparadha*, which will manifest as disease
- ✓ The concept of *Parinama*, (or the effect of time upon us), refers to the impact of seasonal change, the aging process, day/night rhythms, etc. The development of disease arises from the failure of the physical body to adequately adapt to these time-related changes by following *Dinacharya* & *Ritucharya*.

Ayurveda provides a complete Lifestyle Management regimen *via* a series of regulated regimens including

Dinacharya, *Ritucharya*, *Panchakarma* and *Rasayana* therapies. *Sadvritta* and *AacharaRasayana* must be incorporated in healthy lifestyle to maintain psychosomatic health.

Ayurveda Management of Life Style Disorders^[7-11]

✓ **Ahara:** Ayurveda regards *Ahara* as an important element, in addition to *Sattvic* food; it promotes five aspects that should be included when going to consume *Ahara* as mentioned in **Table 2**.

Table 2: Various aspects related to the *Ahara* for healthy well being.

Ayurvedic Principle	Significance
<i>Manasika Prasannata</i>	A positive mental attitude supports proper functioning of <i>Agni</i> and results proper formation of <i>Rasa Dhatu</i> .
<i>Jala Sevana Kala</i>	Drinking water about 30 minutes before meals facilitates digestion by softening the food bolus and supporting <i>Agni</i> . Limited water intake during meals may be beneficial depending on <i>Dosha</i> and water intake immediately after meals weakens <i>Jatharagni</i> .
<i>Matravat Ahara</i>	Food should be taken in appropriate quantity, leaving adequate space in the stomach for digestion, movement of <i>Vata</i> and insufficient intake may disturbs <i>Agni</i> and leads to <i>Ama</i> formation.
<i>Ahara Devata Bhava</i>	Consuming food with gratitude enhances its nourishing capacity and positively influences mental health. It promotes <i>Sattva Vriddhi</i> .
<i>Sattvic Ahara Sevana</i>	<i>Sattvic Ahara</i> promotes <i>Sattva Guna</i> , leading to clarity of mind, mental stability, peace, and purity of consciousness.

The eight factors comprising the *Ashta Ahara Vidhi Visheshayatana* determine if food is effective in providing our bodies with health benefits or is harmful to overall well-being:

1. *Prakriti* – Natural Quality of food.
 2. *Karana* – Food preparation by a method of processing.
 3. *Samyoga* – How the multiple components (yogic) interact with each other.
 4. *Rashi* – How much food is consumed.
 5. *Desha* – Location where the food originated.
 6. *Kala* – When the food is consumed (time of eating).
 7. *Upayogasamstha* – Guidelines or Laws of how food should be ingested.
 8. *Upayokta* – The individual or body that ingests the food.
- ✓ ***Dinacharya:*** Ayurveda, in the interest of accessing the full benefits of a healthy daily routine, recommends beginning with complete awareness of all daily activities each day, waking up early enough to engage in all the natural physical urges as they occur, expelling all bodily waste at the proper time, and performing *Abhyanga*.
- ✓ ***Ritucharya:*** Each season has established guidelines for lifestyle and dietary habits; that allow the body to adapt to seasonal changes smoothly without negatively affecting its internal homeostasis.
- ✓ ***Rasayana and Apunarbhav Chikitsa:*** Ayurvedic medicine has a special classification system known as *Rasayana* that includes herbs and supplements intended to provide nutrition which supports the body in recovering from illnesses as well as providing medicinal benefits. Many *Rasayana* products provide nutrients and have rejuvenating effects through the strengthening of *Agni Bala*, by direct nourishment and through *Srotoprasadana*. Through the use of *Rasayana*, one may regain and maintain good health and well-being.

✓ ***Sadvritta:*** Ayurveda also include ethical codes of conduct and behaviour for living a healthy lifestyle, which mainly includes establishing a set time for sleeping and waking up, not doing excessive physical work and not suppressing natural urges as well as social behaviours that include being compassionate toward others.

✓ ***AacharaRasayana:*** *Charaka Samhita* refers to *Achar Rasayan*, which attains its benefit by exhibiting proper conduct and discipline. *Charaka* explains the difference between *Achar* and *Rasayan* to be that *Achar* indicates proper conduct and discipline, while *Rasayan* means to restore health and youthfulness or longevity. While *Rasayana* mainly focuses on drugs and herbal remedies, *Achar Rasayan* focuses on mental discipline and a regular ethical lifestyle for achieving sustainable health and avoiding disease. Therefore; according to *Charaka*, an individual can use *Achar Rasayan* as a substitute for drugs and herbs to obtain the benefits of *Rasayana* by following a path of truthfulness, non-violence, absence of anger, calmness of mind, pleasant speech, compassion, impersonal charity, respect for parents and teachers, equality to all, self-control, moderation in sexual activities, non-use of intoxicants; observance of a proper sleep and waking cycle; and the observance of spiritual disciplines, such as *Japa* or *Tapa*. The benefits of *Achar Rasayan* enhance the physical strength, mental stability, immunity, and longevity of an individual by maintaining balance among *Doshas*, maintaining *Ojas* (the essence of all physical life), and preventing *Prajnaparadha* (the fundamental cause of most psychosomatic and lifestyle-related diseases). The concept of *Achar Rasayan* thus plays an important role in the Ayurvedic system as it exists in three stages: promotive, preventive, and curative.

- ✓ **Panchakarma:** Ayurveda uses *Panchakarma* as a way to remove toxins from the body through its five cleansing practices like Vaman, Virechana, Vasti, Nasya and Raktamokshana, that helps balancing *Doshas* thus provides profound calming effects on both the mind and the body. After completing the *Panchakarma* process, individuals may feel more energized, rejuvenated and less fatigued.
11. Chandola HM. Lifestyle disorders: Ayurveda with lots of potential for prevention. *Ayu.*, Jul., 2012; 33(3): 327.

CONCLUSION

Lifestyle interventions, especially dietary adjustments are effective at preventing the onset of lifestyle disorders. These changes to one's lifestyle are most beneficial if adopted early on, and continuing to adhere to the Ayurvedic dietary recommendations (such as *Ashtavidha Ahara Visheshayatana*, avoiding *Viruddha Ahara*, and following *Dvadasha Ashana Vidhi*) that can help to prevent or manage lifestyle diseases. Ayurveda states that lifestyle significantly contributes to the development, progression, and prevention of disease. Long-term misuse of *Vihara*; also leads to the imbalance of *Doshas*, decreased *Agni*, *Ama* accumulation and blocked *Srotas*. Therefore, following proper practices of *Dinacharya*, *Ritucharya*, *Sadvritta* and *Achar-rasayan* as described in ayurveda are imperative for preventing and managing lifestyle diseases.

REFERENCES

1. Sastri Kasinath, Chaturvedi Gorkhnath, Charakasamhita, Chaukhambha Bharati Academy Charaka sutra Matrasheetiyaadhyaya, 2020; 5.
2. Sastri Kasinath, Chaturvedi Gorkhnath, Charakasamhita, Chaukhambha Bharati Academy, Charaka Vimana Rasavimana&Trividhakukshiya Vimana, 2020; 1: 2.
3. Sastri Ambikadutta, Sushrutasamhita, Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthana Sushruta Chikitsa sthana Anagatabadhapratishehaadhaya, 2018; 28.
4. Tripathy Bramhananda, Ashtanga hridaya, Chaukhambhasubharatiprakashan, sutra sthana chapter Dinacharya & chapter Ritucharya, 2014; 2: 3.
5. Priyavrat Sharma Carak Samhita (Text with English Translation) Volume-1, Chaukhambha Orientalia, Varanasi, Reprint, 2017.
6. Management of Lifestyle Disorders with Tenets of Ayurveda. Ayushdhara [Internet]. 2022 Jul. 8 [cited 2025 Dec. 24]; 9(3): 50-3.
7. Susrutasamhitas, Shastri Ambika dutta editors, Chaukhambha Sanskrit sansthan, Varanasi, reprint edition 2014, Sutra sthana - 46/475.
8. Bhavmishra, BhavaprakashSamhita by Chunekar K.C.; Chaukhambha Bharti Academy 2013, Purvakhanda-5/117 17.
9. Susrutasamhitas, Shastri Ambika dutta editors, Chaukhambha Sanskrit sansthan, Varanasi, reprint edition 2014, Sutra sthana - 46/468-470.
10. Bhavmishra, BhavaprakashSamhita by Chunekar K.C.; Chaukhambha Bharti Academy 2013, Utterkhanda-5/117 18.